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Connotative Associations of Electoral Candidate Mentions in Swiss Newspapers

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Abstract

To what extent the mass media cover election campaigns fairly or, on the contrary, whether they cover elections in biased way, is a perennial debate among researchers, experts, political parties and citizens. We study the coverage of election candidates in the German-Swiss media for the federal elections of 2015, 2019 and 2023. By fine-tuning a large language model and examining the generated data, we show that the coverage of political candidates varies systematically according to their gender, age and party affiliation. The variances relate to political issues that are typically associated with the corresponding characteristics of the candidates and are mainly found in more recent election years and with new candidates. In the 2015 elections and among incumbents, it is only party identification that explains some of the differences in the media coverage of electoral candidates.

Introduction

The assessment of the role of the mass media (print and online newspapers, television channels or radio stations) in democratic elections has changed considerably in recent decades. Until a few years ago, the debate about the mass media as the fourth estate revolved mainly around the extent to which the media provide (or should provide) sufficient quality information about parties and candidates (Falck et al., 2020, Schudson, 2008). In line with many observations, Farnsworth and Lichter (2012) resumed that a functioning democracy “depends on a *fair* and critical news media to investigate public wrongdoing and to evaluate *objectively* the claims of the self-interested partisans who populate the fields of politics.” (Farnsworth & Lichter, 2012, 548). Hence, the most serious shortcoming was seen as the increasing tendency of journalistic reporting to focus on individual candidates and political competition (“horse race” and “clickbait” journalism) rather than on political content (Chiang & Knight, 2011, Banducci & Hanretty, 2014).

This relatively demanding expectation of the role of the mass media in election campaigns seems to have given way to a more sober understanding over the last years. Recent studies increasingly focus on the detection of biased reporting or even disinformation (Rodrigo-Ginés, Carrillo-de-Albornoz, & Plaza, 2024). On the one hand, this is related to increasing political polarisation and the sharp rise of populism, both of which also lead to targeted campaigns against the media (Hameleers, 2021, Soontjens, Van Remoortere, & Walgrave, 2021). On the other hand, it is linked to changes in the media system such as increasing competitive pressure and, above all, the emergence of online news and social media (Agirdas, 2015, Spinde, et al., 2023).¹

A consistent argument is that if the media are indeed becoming more biased, they are providing less of the information that voters need to properly evaluate politicians and parties and hold them to account in elections (Wolton, 2019, Falck et al., 2020, Lichter, 2017). We are able to examine part of this conclusion by looking at newspaper reports on

¹ News read online and shared on social media is now the main source of information for around half of Swiss citizens, compared to around a third ten years ago (Thommen, Eichenberger, & Sasso, 2024).

candidates for the last three federal election campaigns in Switzerland (2015, 2019 and 2023). From these reports, we compile text paragraphs mentioning election candidates, which are, in combination with meta-data on the candidates and election campaigns, used to fine-tune a large language model (LLM). We subsequently let the LLM generate 2.6 million text paragraphs for different demographic and political characteristics of electoral candidates and explore these texts by looking at the connotative meanings of candidate mentions. In the following, we first discuss the state of the literature in political communication on candidate-related differences in media coverage. We then discuss our data and methodological approach before presenting the results.

Electoral candidates in the media

Our point of departure is the reciprocal relationship that the journalists and the candidates are locked into with each other (Midtbø, 2011). Politicians generally depend on journalists for publicity, while journalists, in turn, depend on politicians to provide interesting news that allows them to entertain their audiences and survive financially (Strömbäck & Dimitrova, 2006). In recent years, this reciprocal relationship has evolved through developments such as increasing economic competition and media concentration, and the emergence of fast-paced news formats (Esser & Matthes, 2013, Hamborg, Donnay, & Gipp, 2019). Particularly in light of the increasing pressure to prepare their news easily for publication on social media (Spinde et al., 2023), journalists are thought to be increasingly introducing unwelcome forms of reporting such as stereotyping, scandalisation or negativity (Kang & Yang, 2022). However, as Nyhan (2012) rightly points out, there are still many journalistic norms and practices that limit the extent to which journalists allow such bias. We therefore suggest that while journalists may well introduce bias (unconsciously or consciously) into their reporting, most are still committed to providing voters with at least minimal information about a wide range of candidates in a way that enables voters to evaluate the political personnel they elect (Norris, 1999, Bennett, 1988).

Journalists also encounter politicians who are increasingly experienced and competent in dealing with the media. In this respect, Midtbø (2011) distinguishes between new and established candidates. New candidates depend on media attention in order to jumpstart their political career. They therefore increasingly seek the media spotlight with strategically planned campaigns. Established candidates, however, are “blame-avoiding politicians” (Midtbø, 2011, 226). They weigh every word and are quick to blame the media because they are worried about their reputation. In line with this, Soontjens, Van Remoortere and Walgrave (2021) have shown that this 'hostile media effect', the idea that the news is biased against one's own party, is common among politicians.

Despite these profound changes in the way journalists deal with politicians, precise empirical results on the strength, nature and evolution of differences in the mass media coverage of electoral campaigns are still rare. Therefore, we ask:

How are differences in media content related to demographic and political characteristics of election candidates?

Possible links between differences in media content and varying news production processes in newsrooms (c.f. Agirdas, 2015) are beyond the scope of the study. The same applies to the possible effects of such differences on newspaper readership and thus on the course of the electoral contest (Lengauer & Johann, 2013). In addition, we cannot provide information on other types of differences in media coverage, especially in relation to gatekeeping, i.e. inequalities in the visibility of candidates in the media (Rodrigo-Ginés, Carrillo-de-Albornoz, & Plaza, 2024, Groeling, 2013). Finally, we provide evidence only for the media system as a whole, and not for individual media titles or different editorial formats in the newspapers (Eberl, 2019, Tresch, 2012).

Connotative associations of candidate mentions

For the purposes of our study, we assume that the content-related evaluation of the electoral candidates by journalists is defined in the context of their mentions. Linguistically, this contextual evaluation can be understood as the connotative associations of the candidate's mentions, which can be localised by the most appropriate words surrounding

this mention (Kroeger, 2022). A different connotative meaning for different candidates may or may not be a bias. It can also signal a different evaluative statement that is informative for voters.

Following Gross, Shalizi and Gelman (2012), we refer to bias, or misrepresentation, when the news describes the characteristics or behaviour of candidates on the basis of their personal characteristics rather than on the basis of their expertise or experience relevant to the office for which they are running. Greene and Lühiste (2017), for example, report gender bias in media coverage of European elections. They show that media reinforce specific stereotypes by linking “easy-to-observe descriptive traits, such as gender”, to issue statements that are “historically connected to these groups” (Greene & Lühiste, 2017, 717). Conversely, we can speak of journalistic evaluation when the information published refers to relevant skills and experience without being influenced by specific personal characteristics of politicians.

In addition to gender, the age of politicians is a fundamental personality characteristic of candidates that, to our knowledge, has not yet been examined for differences in media coverage. And in terms of gender, when it comes to how the media report on female politicians compared to male politicians, the findings in the literature are still, at least to some extent, different (Van der Pas & Aaldering, 2020). For example, while Midtbø (2011) measures a more positive tone in the coverage of female politicians, Lavery (2013) finds little of this. And while Gessler, Gilardi and Kubli (2024) as well as Greene and Lühiste (2017) measure a strong connection between news about female politicians and gender-specific topics such as gender equality policy, the results by Rohrbach, Fiechtner, Schönhagen and Puppis (2020) do not provide enough comparable evidence.

The second major strand of literature on differences in media coverage about candidates in election campaigns looks at partisan imbalances (see Groeling, 2013), and again the results are inconclusive. Some studies have found that the media are generally linking certain parties and candidates to specific issues and that they report more positively on certain parties than others (Falck et al., 2020). Other studies, on the other hand, have provided comparable evidence only for individual media titles, not for the media

system as a whole (Lengauer & Johann, 2013). Despite this uncertainty, we hypothesise the following:

H 1: Demographic (age, gender) and political (party affiliation) characteristics of electoral candidates are linked to connotative associations that evoke issues historically linked to the groups associated with these characteristics.

Kim, Eunji, Lelkes and McCrain (2022) and Rohrbach, Fiechtner, Schönhagen and Puppis (2020) rightly point out that intervening variables moderate the relationship between political and demographic characteristics and media coverage. On the one hand, the differences may vary according to the professional experience of the politicians (Soontjens, Van Remoortere, & Walgrave, 2021). For example, it seems plausible that younger politicians who already have parliamentary experience do not receive any different kind of media attention than incumbents of a different age. We therefore expect the following second hypothesis to hold:

H2: The connection between candidate characteristics and differences in media coverage is moderated for incumbents.

Data and Methods

Previous approaches to measuring candidate-specific differences in political coverage have focused on manual annotations, topic models or classifications using statistical models, network algorithms, transformer models or LLMs (c.f. Cruz, Rocha, & Cardoso, 2019, Alizadeh, et al., 2025). With the exception of topic models, all of the approaches used so far rely on human annotation, either to generate training data or directly to generate results. For this study, we decided to bypass the manual annotation step because it has led to persistent criticism of subjectivity in the definition and conceptualisation of differences in media coverage (Groeling, 2013, Nyhan, 2012). We therefore propose an inductive approach involving the fine-tuning of an LLM followed by data augmentation.

Our study covers the election campaign reports of most German-Swiss media titles (c.f. Wüest, Krell, Wirz, & Meier, 2024, and table A.1 in the Appendix). Unfortunately,

single titles that are important for the political discourse in Switzerland, such as the Republik, are missing, because they are not listed in available databases. On the whole, however, our sample covers the entire spectrum of the German-Swiss newspaper landscape, especially in terms of political orientation and type of newspaper.

In a first step, we select all articles in which at least one candidate was mentioned in the 2015, 2019 and 2023 federal elections. The analysis was then restricted to the text passages surrounding the mentions of candidates, i.e. two sentences before and after the sentence with the mention of a candidate. This enables us to link the media's use of language directly to the personal characteristics of the candidates in order to establish their connotative associations. In total, we are able to use 411 271 text paragraphs. Table A.1. in the appendix lists the number of these text passages for each newspaper title and in each election year.

The subsequent step is to finetune the LLM LLäMmlein 120M² with the text paragraphs. Larger versions of the LLäMmlein model rank as the best decoder model for German, consistently matching or surpassing models with similar parameter sizes. Furthermore, the 120 million parameter model is small enough so it can run on any laptop computer, which is why our analysis could be replicated without any specific technological infrastructure. We ran the fine-tuning for three epochs, each with 117 991 steps.

The text passages described above as well as candidate-, article- and election-specific meta-data serve as input for the fine-tuning. More specifically, each row in our initial dataset starts with the meta-data (e.g. gender and party affiliation of the politician mentioned and the election year) and ends with the text paragraph cut from the corresponding media article.

At the candidate level, we include gender (male, female and non-binary defined politicians in the category female), party affiliation (the big six parties and all other parties in a residual category), incumbency status for the job they are running for, the council the politicians are running for (National Council, Council of States or both) and

² German Tinyllama 120 million, see <https://www.informatik.uni-wuerzburg.de/datascience/projects/nlp/llammlein/> [accessed on March, 18, 2025]

the candidates' age (below 45 years, 45 years to 55 years, above 55 years). At the article level, we distinguish between media articles related to Swiss politics (and therefore approximately also related to the election campaign) and articles unrelated to Swiss politics. At the election level, we simply distinguish the three different election years (2023, 2019 and 2015). Figure 1 shows the distributions of the initial text paragraphs by gender, age and party affiliation and table A.2 in the appendix lists randomly selected initial text paragraphs including their meta-data configuration.

During the fine-tuning process, the model is trained to generate text based on the meta-data and news article paragraphs. It is hypothesised that the LLM, which is designed to replicate texts with a high degree of fidelity, will also replicate the differences in the media reports on electoral candidates. Consequently, the resulting text distributions from these replication processes can then be examined and compared to identify shifts in connotative associations as follows:

$$P(T|M_1) \neq P(T|M_2) \text{ for } M_1, M_2 \in \mathcal{M} \implies \exists \text{ connotative associations}$$

where \mathcal{M} is the set of metadata configurations and T is a random variable representing the generated texts

Figure 1: Distribution of text paragraphs by selected meta-data

In the third step, the prior distributions of texts are approximated as a function of the different meta-data (Li, Si, Guo, Yang, & Cao, 2024). This data augmentation is accomplished by the extraction of text paragraphs from a finetuned model, encompassing all metadata configurations. This process is executed with a scale factor of 5 and a temperature of 0.8, resulting in the generation of 2,6 million text paragraphs.

In order to render the connotative associations in the text paragraphs human-readable, it is first necessary to filter the semantically most meaningful word types – nouns, adjectives and verbs – from the text paragraphs. Table A.3. in the appendix provides illustrative examples of such generated and tokenized texts. We then extract the stems for all words and calculate the tf-idf³ distributions of these filtered words in the texts of each category. The tf-idf weights words in a category that occur frequently in the texts of this category positively, but at the same time, words that generally occur frequently in all texts negatively. This process enables the identification of prominent, or typical words for each category, thereby facilitating meaningful comparisons between the meta-data categories (Kroeger, 2022). The tf-idf weighting also serves to impede the replication of initial imbalances that are observed in the frequency of certain words, for example the fact that around two thirds of the mentions are of male candidates. For the final analysis, we will employ a regression with the metadata serving as independent variables and the cosine similarity of the tf-idf distributions of the texts of each metadata combination to all other texts serving as the dependent variable.

³ Tf stands for term frequency, and idf for inverse document frequency (Spärck Jones, 1972).

Analysis

Figure 2 illustrates the connotative associations, operationalized as the 30 most prominent words that occur in the word contexts of the candidate mentions, according to the candidate's gender. The prominence of the words is thereby determined by their tfidf values. Despite the fact that these results only permit a descriptive overview and the classification does not always appear clear, interesting patterns can nevertheless be identified. The mentions of female candidates are strongly associated with words connected to cultural and education policy (*kulturvermittlung, chefredaktion, kulturhauptstadt, gala, oberstufenlehrer*) as well as ecology, animal welfare and health (*umweltschädlich, schlechtwetter, biodiversität, leinenzwang, gesundheit, privatspitäler, abstinenz*). In contrast, the mentions of male candidates are much more likely to be related to the election campaigns (*parlamentarierring, parlamentsmandat, kantonalpartei, knochenarbeit*), the institutional work of politicians (*vernehmlassungsantrag, kalenderjahr, kantonskanzlei, mantelerlass*), conspiracy theories (*coronaskeptiker, fake, baumgabel, dubios, zweifelhaft*) and economic policy (*marktverzerrung, binnenwirtschaft, bankensystem*).

Figure 2: Most prominent words in the contexts of candidate mentions by gender

The connotative associations exhibited by the different age groups also demonstrate clear differences (see Figure 3). Younger politicians (under 45 years old) are often discussed in the media in connection with words related to crime and internal security issues (*verbrechensbekämpfung, integrationsgesetz, spritze, strassenbeleuchtung, missbrauch*), entertainment (*bestseller, fototermin, schminke, bespielen, unvoreilhaft*) and youth-specific policy areas such as military service, youth work, education, job choice and voting (*diensttage, freischaffend, wählerausweis, berufliche, jugendarbeit, bildungsguthaben, wahlinserat*).

The mentions of middle-aged politicians (between 45 and 55 years old) are frequently linked to connotative associations linked to fundamental issues (political, philosophical, theological; *verteilungsfrage, vertragsstaat, theologie, kirchgemeindehaus, grundsatzabstimmung, hauptbotschaft*) or some sort of crisis management (*sparbeschluss, zauberwort, türöffner, talsohle, notlösung, notfallversorgung, kriminalisieren*). The mentions of older politicians (more than 55 years old), finally, often have foreign and regulatory policy (*europafreundlich, kriegsmaterialexporte, spitzendiplomat, fremdenfeindlich, schutzmassnahme, werbeverbot, verfassungswidrig, planungsstopp*) as well as cost and fiscal policy (*wohnbaufäche, aktienbestand, privatsektor, gebührenhöhe, staatssteuer*) connotations.

Figure 3: Most prominent words in the contexts of candidate mentions by age

The political leanings of the candidates align well with the thematic spectrum of connotative associations in Figures 4A and 4B. The SVP is predominantly associated with industrial and budgetary policy issues (*verkehrsunternehmen, bruttoertrag, exportmarkt, immobilienvermögen, stahlbau, eigentümerverband, krankenkassenbeitrag, preiszuschlag*), while its association with immigration and integration (*mohrenkopf, flüchtlingsdramen*) is comparatively marginal. The Social Democrats (SP) are associated with redistribution and social policy (*gewaltmonopol, sozialarbeiterin, familienorganisation, pensionskassengesetz, lohndossier*) as well as human rights issues (*Uiguren, wegschauen, datenschutzrecht, migrationspolitiker, sexarbeiterinnen*). The FDP is closely intertwined with corporate and austerity policy associations (*firmeninhaber, exportmarkt, impulsprogramm, wirtschaftsmodell, muttergesellschaft, steuerschätzungen, nfa, sanierungskredit*). Nevertheless, FDP candidates are also frequently linked with European and migration policy issues (*EU, flüchtlingswelle, asylmissbrauch, flüchtlingsstatus*), and, perhaps somewhat surprisingly, even more so than SVP candidates. Reporting on Mitte candidates is chiefly concerned with transport and energy policy (*ausgleichsfond, bahnübergänge, stilllegen, solarenergiepreis, velobrücke*) as well as parliamentary and administrative work (*prüfauftrag, kanton, parteivizepräsidentin, überweisen, fraktionsvorsitzende, staatsangestellte*).

The Green Party (GPS) has only a limited association with ecological issues (*infrastrukturanlage, energiefachfrau, umweltbericht, konzessionsbericht, klimasünde*), while words related to economics are more prominent (*fürsorge, gutverdienende, mehrbetrag, inflationär, verfilzen, bankgarantie, immobilienindustrie*). Finally, the GLP is clearly associated with ecological issues (*klimajugendliche, klimaanliegen, gebäudeversicherer, hochmoor*), however, it also has distinct technocratic associations with many prominent words linked to corporate policy (*investitionsvertrag, gesamtvorstand, grossaktionärin, mehrheitsbeteiligung, privateigentümer*) as well as transport and spatial planning (*bahnübergänge, stadtkantone, verkehr, grossraumplanung*).

Figure 4A: Most prominent words in the contexts of candidate mentions by party affiliation (I)

Figure 4B: Most prominent words in the contexts of candidate mentions by party affiliation (II)

Table 1 presents a more systematic comparison of the differences in the texts. The models show correlations between demographic and political characteristics of the candidates and the cosine similarity between the different tf-idf distributions. Positive estimates indicate greater similarity between the texts, while negative estimates indicate greater differences in the tf-idf distributions. The basic model 1 shows slightly greater differences in the coverage of female candidates and in the coverage of under 45-year-olds compared to the reference category of 45-55-year-olds. In terms of the parties, the candidates of the Greens (GPS) and also the SVP exhibit slightly greater differences in their respective tf-idf distributions, while the differences for the GLP appear to be very pronounced. Together with the differences found in the lists of the most prominent words across the two genders, the three age demographics, and the six political parties, these findings offer additional subtle evidence that lends support to the validity of hypothesis 1.

Table 1: Linear regressions of candidate characteristics on text similarities

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
	Estimate (p)	Estimate (p)	Estimate (p)
(Intercept)	0.708 (***)	0.740 (***)	0.689 (***)
Female	-0.025 (*)	-0.034	-0.017
Age (ref=45-55)			
<45	-0.029 (*)	-0.032	-0.016
>55	-0.001	-0.015	-0.001
Parties (ref=Mitte)			
GPS	-0.043 (*)	-0.072 (*)	-0.026
SP	0.013	-0.013	0.007
GLP	-0.103 (***)	-0.118 (***)	-0.085 (***)
FDP	0.012	-0.020	0.048 (*)
SVP	-0.039 (*)	-0.069 (*)	-0.034
Incumbent	0.011	0.012	0.051
Council (ref=national council)			
Council of states	-0.140 (***)	-0.144 (***)	-0.144 (***)
Both councils	-0.143 (***)	-0.143 (***)	-0.143 (***)
Politics	0.269 (***)	0.269 (***)	0.269 (***)
Election (ref=2015)			
2019	0.016	-0.003	0.016
2023	0.265 (***)	0.134 (**)	0.264 (***)
2019 x Female		0.014	
2023 x Female		0.011	
2019 x <45		-0.010	
2023 x <45		0.040	
2019 x >55		0.002	
2023 x >55		0.067 (*)	
2019 x GPS		0.037	
2023 x GPS		0.072	
2019 x SP		0.030	
2023 x SP		0.075	
2019 x GLP		-0.026	
2023 x GLP		0.148 (**)	
2019 x FDP		0.031	
2023 x FDP		0.098 (*)	
2019 x SVP		0.009	
2023 x SVP		0.139 (**)	
Incumbent x Female			-0.015
Incumbent x <45			-0.025
Incumbent x >55			-0.001
Incumbent x GPS			-0.039
Incumbent x SP			0.009
Incumbent x GLP			-0.042
Incumbent x FDP			-0.069 (*)
Incumbent x SVP			-0.013
Adjusted R ²	0.61	0.61	0.61
F-statistic	61.54 (14/536)	29.94 (30/520)	39.76 (22/528)

Levels of significance: ***=0.001, **=0.01, *=0.05

Model 2 uses the interaction between the characteristics of the candidates and the election year to test whether the correlations decrease over time as postulated in hypothesis 2. With respect to age and gender differences, the relationship between the tf-idf differences actually decreases as soon as age groups and genders are considered over time. The differences between the parties, in contrast, largely remain the same across the various election years. Hypothesis 2 therefore has to be rejected.

A similar result can be seen for the incumbency status of candidates (see Model 3 in Table 1). The differences in reporting between genders and age groups are considerably narrower for incumbents. For newly aspiring candidates, in contrast, the differences are significant. With regard to party affiliations, however, the media do not appear to distinguish between incumbents and non-incumbents. Hence, hypothesis 3 only holds, to some extent, for age and gender.

Discussion

We have presented results on the newspaper coverage of election candidates in the German-Swiss media for the federal elections of 2015, 2019 and 2023. We have fine-tuned an LLM with text paragraphs containing candidate mentions and then had the trained model generate a large number of texts. Using these texts, we were able to show that the coverage of political candidates varies systematically according to their gender, age and party affiliation. The observed variances in the coverage are associated with political issues, that are typically linked to the corresponding groups of candidates. Since this applies mainly to new candidates, we assume that the media use personal characteristics as shortcut for their reporting when they know too little about candidates. This is problematic because voters are then provided with too little information for their voting decision.

Our analysis also has some limits. The tf-idf analysis revealed some connotative associations that were difficult or impossible to place in the context of the federal election campaigns. To resolve these doubtful cases, we would have to analyze them in greater depth in the generated texts, for example by analyzing their word embeddings.

In a next step, we could also focus on individual media titles or different journalistic formats and thus include media-specific factors such as the type of newspaper or the target audience.

Literature

- Agirdas, C. (2015). What Drives Media Bias? New Evidence From Recent Newspaper Closures. *Journal of Media Economics* 28(3), 123-141.
- Alizadeh, M., Kubli, M., Samei, Z., Dehghani, S., Zahedivafa, M., Bermeo, J. D., . . . Gilardi, F. (2025). Open-source LLMs for text annotation: a practical guide for model setting and fine-tuning. *Journal of Computational Social Science* 8(17).
- Banducci, S., & Hanretty, C. (2014). Comparative Determinants of Horse-Race Coverage. *European Political Science Review* 6(4), 621-640.
- Bennett, L. W. (1988). *News: The Politics of Illusion*. Pearson Longman.
- Branton, R. P., & Dunaway, J. (2009). Slanted Newspaper Coverage of Immigration: The Importance of Economics and Geography. *Policy Studies Journal* 37(2), 190-292.
- Chiang, C.-F., & Knight, B. (2011). Media bias and influence: Evidence from newspaper endorsements. *The Review of economic studies* 78(3), 795-820.
- Cruz, A. F., Rocha, G., & Cardoso, H. L. (2019). On sentence representations for propaganda detection: From handcrafted features to word embeddings. *Proceedings of the 2nd Workshop on NLP for Internet Freedom: Censorship, Disinformation, and Propaganda* (pp. 107-112). Hong Kong, China: Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Eberl, J.-M. (2019). Lying press: Three levels of perceived media bias and their relationship with political preferences. *Communications* 44(1), 5-32.
- Esser, F., & Matthes, J. (2013). Mediatization effects on political news, political actors, political decisions, and political audiences. In H. Kriesi, S. Lavanex, F. Esser, J. Matthes, M. Bühlmann, & D. Bochler, *Democracy in the age of globalization and mediatization* (pp. 177-201). Palgrave.
- Falck, F., Marstaller, J., Stoehr, N., Maucher, S., Ren, J., Thalhammer, A., . . . Studer, R. (2020). Measuring Proximity Between Newspapers and Political Parties: The Sentiment Political Compass. *Policy & Internet* 12(3), 1944-2866.
- Farnsworth, S. J., & Lichter, S. R. (2012). Authors' Response: Improving News Coverage in the 2012 Presidential Campaign and Beyond. *Politics & Policy* 40(4), 547-556.
- Gessler, T., Gilardi, F., & Kubli, M. (2024). Advocacy Campaigns and Gender Bias in Media Coverage of Elections. *Political Science Research and Methods*, 1-15.
- Giger, N., Traber, D., Gilardi, F., & Bütikofer, S. (2022). The surge in women's representation in the 2019 Swiss federal elections. *Swiss Political Science Review* 28(2), 361-376.
- Greene, Z., & Lühiste, M. (2017). Symbols of priority? How the media selectively report on parties' election campaigns. *European Journal of Political Research*, 717-739.
- Groeling, T. (2008). Who's the Fairest of them All? An Empirical Test for Partisan Bias on ABC, CBS, NBC, and Fox News. *Presidential Studies Quarterly* 38(4), 631-657.
- Groeling, T. (2013). Media bias by the numbers: Challenges and opportunities in the empirical study of partisan news. *Annual Review of Political Science* 16(1), 129-151.
- Gross, J. H., Shalizi, C. R., & Gelman, A. (2012). Does the US Media Have a Liberal Bias?: A Discussion of Tim Groseclose's Left Turn: How Liberal Media Bias Distorts the American Mind. *Perspectives on Politics* 10(3), 775-779.
- Hamborg F., Donna, K. & Gibbs, B. (2019). Automated identification of media bias in news articles: An interdisciplinary literature review. *International Journal on Digital Libraries* 20(4), 391-415.

- Hameleers, M. (2021). On the Ordinary People's Enemies: How Politicians in the United States, the United Kingdom, and the Netherlands Communicate Populist Boundaries via Twitter and the Effects on Party Preferences. *Political Science Quarterly* 136(3), 487-519.
- Kang, H., & Yang, J. (2022). Quantifying perceived political bias of newspapers through a document classification technique. *Journal of Quantitative Linguistics* 29(2), 127-150.
- Kim, Eunji, Lelkes, Y., & McCrain, J. (2022). Measuring dynamic media bias. *Proceedings National Academy of Sciences* 119(32).
- Kroeger, P. (2022). *Analyzing meaning: An introduction to semantics and pragmatics*. Language Science Press.
- Lavery, L. (2013). Gender Bias in the Media. *Politics & Policy* 41(6), 877-910.
- Lengauer, G., & Johann, D. (2013). Candidate and party bias in the news and its effects on party choice: Evidence from Austria. *Studies in Communication Sciences* 13(1), 41-49.
- Li, Z., Si, L., Guo, C., Yang, Y., & Cao, Q. (2024). Data Augmentation for Text-based Person Retrieval Using Large Language Models. *arXiv Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*.
- Lichter, S. R. (2017). Theories of Media Bias. In K. Kenski, & K. Hall Jamieson, *The Oxford Handbook of Political Communication* (pp. 403-416). Oxford University Press.
- Midtbø, T. (2011). Explaining Media Attention for Norwegian MPs: A New Modelling Approach. *Scandinavian Political Studies* 34(3), 226-249.
- Müller, L. (2014). *Comparing Mass Media in Established Democracies: Patterns of Media Performance*. Palgrave.
- Norris, P. (1999). *Critical Citizen: Global Support for Democratic Government*. Oxford University Press.
- Nyhan, B. (2012). Does the US Media Have a Liberal Bias?: A Discussion of Tim Groseclose's Left Turn: How Liberal Media Bias Distorts the American Mind. *Perspectives on Politics* 10(3), 767-771.
- Riccardo, P., & Snyder, J. M. (2015). Empirical Studies of Media Bias. In S. P. Anderson, J. Waldfogel, & D. Strömberg, *Handbook of Media Economics* (pp. 647-667). Elsevier.
- Rodrigo-Ginés, F.-J., Carrillo-de-Albornoz, J., & Plaza, L. (2024). A systematic review on media bias detection: What is media bias, how it is expressed, and how to detect it. *Expert Systems with Applications Volume 237, Part C*.
- Rohrbach, T., Fiechtner, S., Schönhagen, P., & Puppis, M. (2020). More Than Just Gender: Exploring Contextual Influences on Media Bias of Political Candidates. *The International Journal of Press/Politics* 25(4), 692-711.
- Schudson, M. (2008). *Why Democracies Need an Unlovable Press*. Polity Press.
- Soontjens, K., Van Remoortere, A., & Walgrave, S. (2021). The hostile media: Politicians' perceptions of coverage bias. *West European Politics* 44(4), 991-1002.
- Spärck Jones, K. (1972). A statistical interpretation of term specificity and its application in retrieval. *Journal of Documentation* 23(1), 11-21.
- Spinde, T., Richter, E., Wessel, M., Kulshrestha, J., Donnay, & Karsten. (2023). What do Twitter comments tell about news article bias? Assessing the impact of news article bias on its perception on Twitter. *Online Social Networks and Media* 37-38.
- Strömbäck, J., & Dimitrova, D. V. (2006). Mediatization and Media Interventionism: A Comparative Analysis of Sweden and the United States. *The International Journal of Press/Politics* 16(1), 30-49.
- Thommen, S., Eichenberger, R., & Sasso, S. (2024). *Medienmonitor Schweiz 2023*. Zürich: Publicom & Bundesamt für Kommunikation.
- Tresch, A. (2012). The (Partisan) Role of the Press in Direct Democratic Campaigns: Evidence from a Swiss Vote on European Integration. *Swiss Political Science Review*, 287-304.
- Van der Pas, D. J., & Aldering, L. (2020). Gender differences in political media coverage: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Communication* 70(1), 114-143.
- Wolton, S. (2019). Are Biased Media Bad for Democracy? *American Journal of Political Science* 63(3), 548-562.
- Wüest, B., Krell, R., Wirz, R., & Meier, C. (2024). *Der Wahlkampf 2023 in traditionellen Medien*. Zürich: HWZ Hochschule für Wirtschaft Zürich.

Appendix

Table A.1: List of media titles and number of text passages by election year

Newspaper title	2015	2019	2023	Newspaper title	2015	2019	2023
20 Minuten	3298	2607	1754	Swissinfo.ch	357	501	858
Aargauer Zeitung	5953	6994	5810	Schweiz am Sonntag	2225	-	-
Anzeiger von Uster	119	132	-	Schweizer Bauer	759	933	-
Appenzeller Zeitung	-	5671	2162	Schweizer Familie	10	4	38
Badener Tagblatt	3	-	2702	Schweizer Illustrierte	439	381	212
Basellandschaftliche Zeitung	1905	2395	2957	Schweizer Landliebe	-	-	2
Basler Zeitung	5530	8986	3864	Seetaler Bote	611	432	-
Beobachter	-	-	355	Solothurner Zeitung	2048	4433	3462
Berner Oberländer	-	3885	3659	Sonntagszeitung	739	733	373
Berner Zeitung	7096	9473	4036	Sonntagsblick	825	670	368
Bieler Tagblatt	665	2060	-	St. Galler Tagblatt	4959	5690	2124
Bilanz	73	86	107	Tagblatt der Stadt Zürich	24	307	4971
Blick	2615	2017	5631	Tageswoche	1183	-	-
Bolero	-	-	4	Thalwiler Anzeiger / Sihltaler	-	-	264
Bote der Urschweiz	2542	3346	-	Thuner Tagblatt	-	-	3620
Langenthaler Tagblatt	-	-	3587	Thurgauer Zeitung	2101	5706	2736
Bündner Tagblatt	2376	1810	-	Toggenburger Tagblatt	-	5508	1929
Cash	2941	2239	1452	Urner Zeitung	-	4869	2243
Coopzeitung	6	11	-	Volketswiler	39	7	-
Das Magazin	54	73	47	Walliser Bote	2569	2510	-
Der Bund	6057	9487	3746	Werdenberger & Obertoggenburger	2087	4243	1983
Der Landbote	3020	4345	1653	Wiler Zeitung	-	-	2050
Südostschweiz	2846	2142	-	Willisauer Bote	1144	1216	-
Weltwoche	1167	1036	1343	Zentralschweiz am Sonntag	471	287	-
Wochenzeitung	475	431	194	Zofinger Tagblatt	885	4494	1371
Femina	-	-	10	Zuger Presse	-	-	158
Finanz und Wirtschaft	87	102	577	Zuger Zeitung	-	5250	2453
Freiburger Nachrichten	1443	3261	-	Zugerbieter	-	-	98
Furttaler	147	139	-	Zürcher Oberländer	2107	4497	-
Glattaler	312	158	-	Zürcher Unterländer	1932	4034	3795
Glückspost	-	15	19	Zürichsee-Zeitung	2731	4267	3893
Grenchner Tagblatt	-	-	2409	Encore	-	-	1
Handelszeitung	428	326	992	Landbote	-	-	2288
Infosperber	148	160	-	SRF.ch	4731	6362	2139
Limmattaler Zeitung	1015	3308	2690	Watson	28	3245	-
Luzerner Zeitung	-	7151	5209	Zentralplus	888	1492	-
Medienwoche	40	39	-	Total	110 993	184 157	116 121
Migros-Magazin	68	44	-				
NZZ Folio	-	-	43				
NZZ am Sonntag	887	872	449				
Neue Luzerner Zeitung	5259	-	-				
Neue Zürcher Zeitung	4177	3226	4264				
Tages-Anzeiger	10 904	11 292	4004				
Nidwaldner Zeitung	-	5141	2290				
Obersee Nachrichten	144	42	-				
Obwaldner Zeitung	-	5242	2270				
Oltner Tagblatt	781	1913	2403				
Ostschweiz am Sonntag	457	309	-				
Rümlanger	63	120	-				

Table A.2: Random examples of initial texts for selected meta-data combinations

<p>party=Mitte, gender=Male, age=45-55, incumbency=yes, candidate=national council, issue=politics, election=2019</p>	<p>Martin Landolt sitzt im Frühstücksraum des Hotels Stadthaus in Burgdorf. Das Wetter draussen ist garstig, passend zur Lage der BDP. «Haddern Sie mit der Rolle als Kleinpartei, die nicht zwingend gebraucht wird?»</p>
<p>party=SVP, gender=male, age=<45, incumbency=no, candidate=national council, issue=politics, election=2019</p>	<p>Über die Hälfte aller Gemeinden hätten Schwierigkeiten, ihre politischen Ämter überhaupt noch zu besetzen. Woran liegt das? Mögliche Lösungsansätze, um eine Trendwende herbeizuführen wurden in der Podiumsdiskussion mit Maja Riniker, Nationalratskandidatin FDP, Renate Gautschy, Präsidentin der Aargauer Gemeindeammänner-Vereinigung, Clemens Hochreuter, Nationalratskandidat SVP, und Markus Freitag erörtert. In diversen Kantonen ist der Amtszwang eingeführt worden. Alle an der Diskussion Beteiligten waren sich einig, dass diese extreme Form nicht die gewünschte Qualität der Arbeit liefert.</p>
<p>party=SP, gender=male, age=>55, incumbency=no, candidate=national council, issue=politics, election=2015</p>	<p>Weshalb sollen die Zuger ausgerechnet Sie wählen. Ich will den Zugerinnen und Zugern, welchen eine soziale Gesellschaft, eine intakte Natur und Heimat sowie der schonende Umgang mit Ressourcen wichtig sind, eine Stimme in Bern verleihen. Hubert Schuler ist 58 Jahre alt, ist verheiratet und Vater von zwei Kindern. Der Sozialarbeiter und Leiter des Sozialdienstes Baar wohnt mit seiner Familie in Hünenberg. Politisch ist Schuler Mitglied der SP und kantonaler Parteipräsident.</p>
<p>party=GPS, gender=female, age=<45, incumbency=yes, council=national council, issue=not politics, election=2023</p>	<p>Dem ersten Profil idealtypisch zuzurechnen ist Parteipräsident Balthasar Glättli. Er hat sich aber im Interview mit der «Sonntags-Zeitung» bereits selbst aus dem Rennen genommen. Fraktionschefin Aline Trede sagt, sie sei für den ganzen Auswahlprozess im Lead, darum habe eine eigene Kandidatur für sie keine Priorität. «Aber ich überlege es mir sicher nochmals ganz gut.» Bastien Girod will in den nächsten Tagen in Familie und Partei sondieren, ob er sich zur Verfügung stellt.</p>
<p>party=FDP, gender=female, age=>55, incumbency=no, candidate=national council, issue=not politics, election=2019</p>	<p>Diese gilt es zu reduzieren und zu beseitigen und am Thema dranzubleiben. Es ist ein grosses Handlungsfeld offen, und jeder einzelne ist gefordert. Rosy Schmid (Kantonsrätin FDP, Hildisrieden LU): «Boden mit dem Richtigen füttern». Zur regenerativen Landwirtschaft. Das Wort «regenerative Landwirtschaft» ist längst zu einem Schlagwort geworden und steht für einen Aufbruch.</p>

Table A.3: Random examples of generated and tokenized texts for selected meta-data combinations

party=SP, gender=female, age=>55, incumbency=no, council=national council, issue=politics, election=2019	streng neu ausserordentlich aufgeblockt erledigen sehen erhalten einreichen verlangen kautionspflicht auflage arbeit polizist bewaffnung vorbild arbeitgeber gesetz grosse polizist einstellung gewalttat grenze grenzkontrolle einsatzort motion erfordernis androhung
party=Mitte, gender=female, age=45-55, incumbency=yes, council=national council, issue=politics, election=2015	vergangen erster führen bringen gewinnen merken abbilden sagen nationalratskandidat woche wahlkampf aufmerksamkei bezirk kandidat region leute region werthenstein nähe dorf wahlumfrage thema
party=SVP, gender=male, age=>55, incumbency=yes, council=national council, issue= not politics, election=2023	ehemalig kantonal besetzen ticken mitprägen abstimmen beteiligen urner mitte frage funktion prääsident unterwalden erstellung liste nationalratswahl vorlage stimmrecht kantonalvorstand fall abstimmung ausgangslage
party=GPS, gender=female, age=>55, incumbency=yes, council=national council and council of states, issue=politics, election=2019	neu erste st.galler treten gehören stehen präsentieren umzugsquartier energiegesetz kraft müllhaufen gelände firma module gangsaal abend stadtparlament ständeratskandidaten grüne gast anliegen bedürfnis wunsch
party=FDP, gender=male, age=45-55, incumbency=yes, council=national council, issue=politics, election 2015	kantonal unschön stärken erklären passieren sagen einreichen knatsch finanzhaushalt anlass finanzdirektor rücken ungerechti- keit abstimmungskämpfe problem vizepräsident woche postulat re- gierung